

Non-Friction Bi-National Trades

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Abstract

The author independently developed the following intuition while watching Lecture 19, International Trade: Welfare and Policy, from MIT OCW 14.01 (Fall 2023), Undergraduate Principles of Microeconomics, taught by Prof. Jonathan Gruber: the equilibrium price in international trade does not necessarily satisfy all.

My independent research shows that in non-friction bi-national trade, analysis is too complex for me to solve, but when the relative advantage is symmetric in the ratio, the equilibrium price is guaranteed to be not as good as bidirectional polarized pricing for both nations.

When we can apply this compound polarized pricing, the benefits go beyond economics: for strategic pillar industries characterized by oligopoly or monopoly and are losing money, we can use contracts of bidirectional polarized pricing that benefit all rather than import tax to protect these strategic pillar industries.

1 A Pair of Goods

Table 1: Cost in USD per unit

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
Rose	x	z
Computer	y	w

Note. $yz < xw$, regardless of the choices of goods, or this table will fail.

1.1 Definition of the Rate of Price

Define the rate of price in non-friction bi-national trades:

$$P = ROI + 1, \text{ where only extra } ROI \text{ from the trade is counted as } ROI.$$

E.g., when the US pay y more to produce computers and pay $\frac{xw}{z}$ less to produce roses, $P = \frac{xw}{yz}$.

1.2 When one nation sticks to the domestic price

Assume that there is no friction in the trade and that Ecuador sticks to the domestic price. For each unit of computer, the US produces for the trade, the change in cost for the same goods after the trade is:

Table 2: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
Rose	$-\frac{xw}{z}$	w
Computer	y	$-w$
Total	$-\frac{xw}{z} + y$	0

Note. Ecuador sticks to the domestic price. The US produces 1 more unit of computers and exports them to Ecuador, Ecuador produces 1 less unit of computers and saves w . Ecuador exports roses of the same domestic price as those computers to the US, charging the same price as domestic price.

We call the rate of price when one nation sticks to the domestic price in non-friction bi-national trades, P_0 .

It's unfair because $P_{US} = P_0 = \frac{xw}{yz} > 1$, while $P_{EC} = 1$.

1.3 When two nations share the rate of price

Assume that Ecuador increases the price of the rose in this trade to λ times the domestic price.

Table 3: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
Rose	$-\frac{xw}{\lambda z}$	$\frac{w}{\lambda}$
Computer	y	$-w$
Total	$-\frac{xw}{\lambda z} + y$	$-w + \frac{w}{\lambda}$

Note. Both nations share the same rate of price. The US produces 1 more unit of computers and exports them to Ecuador, Ecuador produces 1 less unit of computers and saves w . Ecuador exports roses of the domestic price of those computers divides λ to the US, charging the same total price as those computers.

Let $P_{US} = P_{EC}$, we get $\frac{P_0}{\lambda} = \lambda$, $\lambda = \sqrt{P_0} = \sqrt{\frac{xw}{yz}}$.

$$P_{Equilibrium} = \frac{P_0}{\lambda} = \sqrt{P_0} = \sqrt{\frac{xw}{yz}}$$

Plugging in λ , we get the final result:

Table 4: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
Rose	$-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}}$
Computer	y	$-w$
Total	$-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}} + y$	$-w + \sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}}$

Note. Both nations share the same rate of price.

1.4 Disadvantage of sharing the rate of price

By intuition, we want the sum of ROI to reach its maximum, and

$$P_1 + P_2 = (ROI_1 + 1) + (ROI_2 + 1) = ROI_1 + ROI_2 + 2$$

So, we want to maximize $P_1 + P_2$ with the restriction that $P_1 = \frac{P_0}{\lambda} \geq 1$ and $P_2 = \lambda \geq 1$, which is the same as $\lambda \in [1, P_0]$.

Calculation shows that the maximum of $ROI_1 + ROI_2$ appears at $\lambda = 1$ or $\lambda = P_0$. And the minimum appears at $\lambda = \sqrt{P_0}$, exactly when the two nations share the rate of price. But we need to prove our intuition.

2 Pairs of Goods

Let C_i represent what the USA is relatively better at producing than Ecuador, let R_i represent what Ecuador is relatively better at producing than the USA.

Notice that for the row C_i or R_i , the index of x, y, z, w should be the same, but to avoid complexity, assume that the index does not influence, which is generally wrong in the real world.

2.1 The Method of Equilibrium. When two nations share the rate of price for each of the two pairs of goods

Table 5: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
R_1	$-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}}$
R_2	$-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}}$
C_1	y	$-w$
C_2	y	$-w$
Total	$2(-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}} + y)$	$2(-w + \sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}})$
Total	$2(-\sqrt{P_0} + 1)y$	$2(-1 + P_0^{-0.5})w$

Note. Both nations share the rate of price for each of the two pairs of goods. For C_1 and R_1 , it begins with the USA producing one more unit of C_1 , then, they use the method in the subsection of "When two nations share the rate of price". The same progress for C_2 and R_2 .

2.2 The Method of Bidirectional Polarization. When one nation sticks to export in the domestic price for one goods while the other nation sticks to export in the domestic price for the other goods for the two pairs of goods

Table 6: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
R_1	$-\frac{xw}{z}$	w
R_2	$-y$	$\frac{yz}{x}$
C_1	y	$-w$
C_2	y	$-w$
Total	$-\frac{xw}{z} + y$	$-w + \frac{yz}{x}$
Total	$(-P_0 + 1)y$	$(-1 + P_0^{-1})w$

Note. One nation sticks to export in the domestic price for one goods while the other nation sticks to export in the domestic price for the other goods for the two pairs of goods. For C_1 and R_1 , it begins with the US producing one more unit of C_1 , using the method in the subsection of "When one nation sticks to the domestic price". For C_2 and R_2 , the US produces one more unit of C_2 , costing extra y , Ecuador produces one less unit of C_2 , and exports the amount of R_2 that costs y in the US and exports in the total price of y .

2.3 Generalized Simpson's Paradox: Comparing Polarization with Equilibrium

Let T represent total.

$$T_{(US,P)} - T_{(US,E)} = -(\sqrt{P_0} - 1)^2 y < 0$$

$$T_{(EC,P)} - T_{(EC,E)} = (P_0^{-0.5} - 1)^2 w > 0$$

When P_0 is near 1, we can estimate that $(P_0^{-0.5} - 1)^2 \approx (\sqrt{P_0} - 1)^2$, then:

$$T_P - T_E = (\sqrt{P_0} - 1)^2 (-y + w)$$

As $P_0 > 1$ $w > y$,

$$T_P - T_E > 0$$

This means that Polarization is good for the US, bad for Ecuador, bad for total wealth. But this is in fact the generalized Simpson's Paradox, and we can solve it.

3 Pairs of Goods with Anti-Simpson Solution

3.1 The Method of Bidirectional Polarization with Anti-Simpson Solution

Table 7: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
R_1	$-\frac{xw}{z}$	w
R_2	$-x$	z
C_1	y	$-w$
C_2	x	$-\frac{xw}{y}$
Total	$-\frac{xw}{z} + y$	$-\frac{xw}{y} + z$
Total	$(-P_0 + 1)y$	$(-P_0 + 1)z$

Note. With anti-Simpson solution: one nation sticks to export in the domestic price for one goods while the other nation sticks to export in the domestic price for the other goods for the two pairs of goods. C_1 and R_1 begin with C_1 of y , C_2 and R_2 begin with R_2 of z .

3.2 The Method of Equilibrium with Anti-Simpson Solution

Table 8: Change in Cost for the Same Goods After the Trade

Goods \ Country	USA	Ecuador
R_1	$-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}}$
R_2	$-x$	z
C_1	y	$-w$
C_2	$\sqrt{\frac{xyz}{w}}$	$-\sqrt{\frac{xzw}{y}}$
Total	$-\sqrt{\frac{xyw}{z}} + y - x + \sqrt{\frac{xyz}{w}}$	$-w + \sqrt{\frac{yzw}{x}} - \sqrt{\frac{xzw}{y}} + z$
Total	$(-\sqrt{P_0} + 1)y + (-1 + P_0^{-0.5})x$	$(-1 + P_0^{-0.5})w + (-\sqrt{P_0} + 1)z$

Note. With anti-Simpson solution: both nations share the rate of price for each of the two pairs of goods. C_1 and R_1 begin with C_1 of y , C_2 and R_2 begin with R_2 of z .

3.3 With Anti-Simpson's Paradox Solution: Comparing Polarization with Equilibrium

Without loss of generality, for a certain i , we can modify our definition of units of R_i and C_i to guaranty $y = z = 1$.

3.4 A Trivial Solution

However, the independence of x and w is so annoying that we consider a trivial case:

$$\frac{x_i}{z_i} = \frac{w_i}{y_i} = q_i$$

In this trivial case:

$$T_{(US,P)} - T_{(US,E)} = -(q-1)^2 < 0$$

$$T_{(EC,P)} - T_{(EC,E)} = -(q-1)^2 < 0$$

$$T_P - T_E = -2(q-1)^2 < 0$$

As it is universally true in a reasonable trade that $q_i > 1$, none of the above inequalities can be equal, which means that both nations win in the anti-Simpson polarization solution when:

$$\frac{x_1}{z_1} = \frac{w_1}{y_1}$$

$$\frac{x_2}{z_2} = \frac{w_2}{y_2}$$

4 Application in Global Trade

4.1 When to Apply

For industries characterized by oligopoly or monopoly, if:

$$\frac{x_1}{z_1} = \frac{w_1}{y_1}$$

$$\frac{x_2}{z_2} = \frac{w_2}{y_2}$$

Then, we can apply this bidirectional polarized pricing. But please be aware that in general the bidirectional polarized pricing does not have the magic of keeping the domestic price for strategic pillar industries. It only rises some import share of strategic pillar industries to the price of domestic price.

4.2 Difficulty in the Negotiation of Equilibrium

It is relatively easier for both sides to agree with the equilibrium price. But the bidirectional polarized pricing means that each polarized pricing is harming one side, that is why we need at least two pairs of goods, so we can get both directions. When there is a polarized pricing that is winning too much, you may need a few polarized pricing of opposite direction to satisfy the opposite. Or, we can pay money for our advantage in polarized pricing.

In conclusion, equilibrium pricing is naturally in equilibrium, but it requires a lot of effort for a bidirectional polarized pricing to reach equilibrium. And for the simplification of negotiation and contracts, we prefer industries characterized by oligopoly or monopoly.

4.3 Benefits

As shown in the tables, when the relative advantage is symmetric in the ratio, bidirectional polarized pricing reduces cost of both nations in non-friction bi-national trade, comparing to the equilibrium price.

What is more, for these industries that are losing money, if we think some of them are strategic pillar industries and want to protect them, with bidirectional polarized pricing, we can get the price of protected higher than the equilibrium price, without paying a penny to these industry. Just set in the contracts that the opposite would maximum their profits in these industries, so that the import price would be as high as domestic price.

References

- [1] Jonathan Gruber, *Lecture 19: International Trade: Welfare and Policy*, MIT OpenCourseWare, 14.01 Principles of Microeconomics, Fall 2023. Available at: <https://ocw.mit.edu/> (Accessed: 29 June 2026).